

*******Overview*******

These datasets are processed to study global-scale impacts of the May 2024 Extreme Geomagnetic Storm on Global Positioning System (GPS) precise point positioning (PPP) solutions by taking advantage of 5800+ stations installed worldwide.

Dataset description:

-Folder 'PPP/0510/'

- Folder 'PPP/0511/'

-Folder 'PPP/0512/'

-Folder 'PPP/0513/'

These folders contain the files including GPS PPP errors for GPS stations during May 10-13, 2024. The dataset format is consistent among files. Each column (from left to right) in the file represents:

- Year
- Month
- Day of Month
- Hour
- Minute
- Second
- Position error in East component (unit: meter)
- Position error in North component (unit: meter)
- Position error in Up component (unit: meter)
- Geometry Dilution of Precision

Dataset description:

-Folder 'ROTI/0510/'

- Folder 'ROTI/0511/'

-Folder 'ROTI/0512/'

-Folder 'ROTI/0513/'

These folders contain the files including the rate of TEC index (ROTI) derived from GPS observations collected during May 10-13, 2024. The dataset format is consistent among files. Each column (from left to right) in the file represents:

- Site
- Hour
- Minute
- Second

Geographic Latitude of Site (unit: degree)
Geographic Longitude of Site (unit: degree)
Height of Site (unit: meter)
Elevation angle (unit: degree)
Azimuth angle (unit: degree)
Geographic Latitude of Ionospheric Pierce Point at 350 km (unit: degree)
Geographic Longitude of Ionospheric Pierce Point at 350 km (unit: degree)
ROTI (unit: TECu/min)
PRN ID of the GPS satellite

-Folder 'TEC'

This folder contains the files including TEC datasets during May 10-13, 2024. These TEC datasets are provided by the Madrigal database. The description of the data format can be found through <http://cedar.openmadrigal.org>.